

On Equitable Coloring of Helm Graph and Gear Graph

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Abstract: The notion of equitable coloring was introduced by Meyer in 1973. In this paper we obtain interesting results regarding the equitable chromatic number $\chi_{=}$ for the Helm Graph H_n , line graph of Helm graph $L(H_n)$, middle graph of Helm graph $M(H_n)$, total graph of Helm graph $T(H_n)$, Gear graph G_n , line graph of Gear graph $L(G_n)$, middle graph of Gear graph $M(G_n)$, total graph of Gear graph $T(G_n)$.

Key Words: Smarandachely equitable k -colorable graph, Equitable coloring, Helm graph, Gear graph, line graph, middle graph and total graph.

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§1. Introduction

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph. If the vertices of G can be partitioned into m classes V_1, V_2, \dots, V_m such that each V_i , ($1 \leq i \leq m$) are independent and $||V_i| - |V_j|| \leq 1$ holds for every pair ($1 \leq i, j \leq k$), where $k \leq m$, then the graph G is said to be *Smarandachely equitable k -colorable*. Particularly, if $k = m$, we abbreviated it to *equitably k -colorable*. The smallest integer k for which G is Smarandachely equitable k -colorable or equitable k -colorable is known as the *Smarandachely equitable chromatic number* or *equitable chromatic number* [1,3,7-10] of G and denoted by $\chi_{=}(G)$, respectively.

This model of graph coloring has many applications. Every time when we have to divide a system with binary conflicting relations into equal or almost equal conflict-free subsystems we can model such situation by means of equitable graph coloring. This subject is widely discussed in literature [3,8-10]. In general, the problem of optimal equitable coloring, in the sense of the number color used, is NP-hard. So we have to look for simplified structure of graphs allowing polynomial-time algorithms. This paper gives such solution for Helm graph and Gear graph families: Helm graph, its line, middle and total graphs; Gear graph, its line, middle and total graphs.

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§2. Preliminaries

The Helm graph H_n is the graph obtained from an n -wheel graph by adjoining a pendent edge at each node of the cycle.

The Gear graph G_n , also known as a bipartite wheel graph, is a wheel graph with a graph vertex added between each pair of adjacent graph vertices of the outer cycle.

The line graph [2,5] of G , denoted by $L(G)$ is the graph with vertices are the edges of G with two vertices of $L(G)$ adjacent whenever the corresponding edges of G are adjacent.

The middle graph [4] of G , is defined with the vertex set $V(G) \cup E(G)$ where two vertices are adjacent iff they are either adjacent edges of G or one is the vertex and the other is an edge incident with it and it is denoted by $M(G)$.

Let G be a graph with vertex set $V(G)$ and edge set $E(G)$. The total graph [2,4,5] of G , denoted by $T(G)$ is defined in the following way. The vertex set of $T(G)$ is $V(G) \cup E(G)$. Two vertices x, y in the vertex set of $T(G)$ are adjacent in $T(G)$ in case one of the following holds: (i) x, y are in $V(G)$ and x is adjacent to y in G . (ii) x, y are in $E(G)$ and x, y are adjacent in G . (iii) x is in $V(G)$, y is in $E(G)$, and x, y are incident in G . Additional graph theory terminology used in this paper can be found in [2,5,9].

§3. Equitable Coloring on Helm Graph

Theorem 3.1 *If $n \geq 4$ the equitable chromatic number of Helm graph H_n ,*

$$\chi_=(H_n) = \begin{cases} 3 & \text{if } n \text{ is even,} \\ 4 & \text{if } n \text{ is odd.} \end{cases}$$

Proof Let H_n be the Helm graph obtained by attaching a pendant edge at each vertex of the cycle. Let $V(H_n) = \{v\} \cup \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\} \cup \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$ where v_i 's are the vertices of cycles taken in cyclic order and u_i 's are pendant vertices such that each $v_i u_i$ is a pendant edge and v is a hub of the cycle.

Case i: If n is even.

Case i-a: If $n = 6k - 2$ for some positive integer k , then set the partition of V as below.

$V_1 = \{v\} \cup \{u_i : 2k + 1 \leq i \leq 6k - 2\}$; $V_2 = \{v_{2i-1} : 1 \leq i \leq 3k - 1\} \cup \{u_{2i} : 1 \leq i \leq k\}$; $V_3 = \{v_{2i} : 1 \leq i \leq 3k - 1\} \cup \{u_{2i-1} : 1 \leq i \leq k\}$. Clearly V_1, V_2, V_3 are independent sets of $V(H_n)$. Also $|V_1| = |V_2| = |V_3| = 4k - 1$, it holds the inequality $||V_i| - |V_j|| \leq 1$ for every pair (i, j) .

Case i-b: If $n = 6k$ for some positive integer k , then set the partition of V as below.

$V_1 = \{v\} \cup \{u_i : 2k + 2 \leq i \leq 6k\}$; $V_2 = \{v_{2i-1} : 1 \leq i \leq 3k\} \cup \{u_{2i} : 1 \leq i \leq k\}$; $V_3 = \{v_{2i} : 1 \leq i \leq 3k\} \cup \{u_{2i-1} : 1 \leq i \leq k + 1\}$. Clearly V_1, V_2, V_3 are independent sets of $V(H_n)$. Also $|V_1| = |V_2| = 4k$ and $|V_3| = 4k + 1$, it holds the inequality $||V_i| - |V_j|| \leq 1$ for

every pair (i, j) .

Case i-c: If $n = 6k + 2$ for some positive integer k , then set the partition of V as below.

$V_1 = \{v\} \cup \{u_i : 2k + 3 \leq i \leq 6k + 2\}$; $V_2 = \{v_{2i-1} : 1 \leq i \leq 3k + 1\} \cup \{u_{2i} : 1 \leq i \leq k + 1\}$;
 $V_3 = \{v_{2i} : 1 \leq i \leq 3k + 1\} \cup \{u_{2i-1} : 1 \leq i \leq k + 1\}$. Clearly V_1, V_2, V_3 are independent sets of $V(H_n)$. $|V_1| = 4k + 1$ and $|V_2| = |V_3| = 4k + 2$, it holds the inequality $||V_i| - |V_j|| \leq 1$ for every pair (i, j) .

In all the three subcases of Case i, $\chi_=(H_n) \leq 3$. Since $\chi(H_n) \geq 3$, $\chi_=(H_n) \geq \chi(H_n) \geq 3$, $\chi_=(H_n) \geq 3$. Therefore $\chi_=(H_n) = 3$.

Case ii: If n is odd.

Case ii-a: If $n = 6k - 3$ for some positive integer k , then set the partition of V as below.

$V_1 = \{v\} \cup \{u_i : 3k + 1 \leq i \leq 5k - 1\}$; $V_2 = \{v_{3i-2} : 1 \leq i \leq 2k - 1\} \cup \{u_{3i} : 1 \leq i \leq k\}$;
 $V_3 = \{v_{3i-1} : 1 \leq i \leq 2k - 1\} \cup \{u_{3i-2} : 1 \leq i \leq k\}$; $V_4 = \{v_{3i} : 1 \leq i \leq 2k - 1\} \cup \{u_{3i-1} : 1 \leq i \leq k\}$. Clearly V_1, V_2, V_3 are independent sets of $V(H_n)$. Also $|V_1| = 3k - 2$ and $|V_2| = |V_3| = |V_4| = 3k - 1$, it holds the inequality $||V_i| - |V_j|| \leq 1$ for every pair (i, j) .

Case ii-b: If $n = 6k - 1$ for some positive integer k , then set the partition of V as below.

$V_1 = \{v\} \cup \{u_i : 3k + 2 \leq i \leq 6k - 1\}$; $V_2 = \{v_{3i-2} : 1 \leq i \leq 2k\} \cup \{u_{3i-1} : 1 \leq i \leq 2k - 1\}$;
 $V_3 = \{v_{3i-1} : 1 \leq i \leq 2k\} \cup \{u_{3i} : 1 \leq i \leq 2k - 1\}$; $V_4 = \{v_{3i} : 1 \leq i \leq 2k - 1\} \cup \{u_{3i-2} : 1 \leq i \leq 2k\}$. Clearly V_1, V_2, V_3 are independent sets of $V(H_n)$. Also $|V_1| = 4k - 2$ and $|V_2| = |V_3| = |V_4| = 4k - 1$, it holds the inequality $||V_i| - |V_j|| \leq 1$ for every pair (i, j) .

Case ii-c: If $n = 6k + 1$ for some positive integer k , then set the partition of V as below.

$V_1 = \{v\} \cup \{u_i : 3k + 2 \leq i \leq 6k + 1\}$; $V_2 = \{v_{3i-2} : 1 \leq i \leq 2k\} \cup \{u_{3i-1} : 1 \leq i \leq 2k - 1\}$;
 $V_3 = \{v_{3i-1} : 1 \leq i \leq 2k\} \cup \{v_n\} \cup \{u_{3i} : 1 \leq i \leq 2k - 1\}$; $V_4 = \{v_{3i} : 1 \leq i \leq 2k\} \cup \{u_1\} \cup \{u_{3i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq 2k - 1\}$. Clearly V_1, V_2, V_3 are independent sets of $V(H_n)$. $|V_1| = |V_3| = |V_4| = 4k$ and $|V_2| = 4k - 1$, it holds the inequality $||V_i| - |V_j|| \leq 1$ for every pair (i, j) .

In all the three subcases of cases (ii), $\chi_=(H_n) \leq 4$. Since $\chi(H_n) \geq 4$, $\chi_=(H_n) \geq \chi(H_n) \geq 4$, $\chi_=(H_n) \geq 4$. Therefore $\chi_=(H_n) = 4$. \square

§4. Equitable Coloring on Line graph, Middle Graph and Total Graph of Helm Graph

Theorem 4.1 *If $n \geq 4$ the equitable chromatic number on line graph of Helm graph $L(H_n)$, $\chi_=(L(H_n)) = n$.*

Proof Let $V(H_n) = \{v\} \cup \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\} \cup \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$ and $E(H_n) = \{e_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{e'_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\} \cup \{e'_n\} \cup \{s_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ where e_i is the edge vv_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$), e'_i is the edge $v_i v_{i+1}$ ($1 \leq i \leq n-1$), e'_n is the edge $v_n v_1$ and s_i is the edge $v_i u_i$ ($1 \leq i \leq n$). By the definition of line graph $V(L(H_n)) = E(H_n) = \{e_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{e'_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{s_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$.

Now, we partition the vertex set of $V(L(H_n))$ as below.

$V_1 = \{e_1, e'_2, s_n\}$; $V_i = \{e_i, e'_{i+1}, s_{i-1} : 2 \leq i \leq n-1\}$; $V_n = \{e_n, e'_1, s_{n-1}\}$. Clearly V_1, V_i, V_n ($2 \leq i \leq n-1$) are independent sets of $L(H_n)$. Also $|V_1| = |V_i| = |V_n| = 3$ ($2 \leq i \leq n-1$), it holds the inequality $\||V_i| - |V_j|\| \leq 1$ for every pair (i, j) . $\chi_{=}(L(H_n)) \leq n$. Since e_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$) forms a clique of order n , $\chi(L(H_n)) \geq n$, $\chi_{=}(L(H_n)) \geq \chi(L(H_n)) \geq n$, $\chi_{=}(L(H_n)) \geq n$. Therefore $\chi_{=}(L(H_n)) = n$. \square

Theorem 4.2 *If $n \geq 5$ the equitable chromatic number on middle graph of Helm graph $M(H_n)$, $\chi_{=}(M(H_n)) = n + 1$.*

Proof Let $V(H_n) = \{v\} \cup \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\} \cup \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$ and $E(H_n) = \{e_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{e'_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\} \cup \{e'_n\} \cup \{s_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ where e_i is the edge vv_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$), e'_i is the edge $v_i v_{i+1}$ ($1 \leq i \leq n-1$), e'_n is the edge $v_n v_1$ and s_i is the edge $v_i u_i$ ($1 \leq i \leq n$). By the definition of middle graph $V(M(H_n)) = V(H_n) \cup E(H_n) = \{v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{e_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{e'_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{s_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$.

Now, we partition the vertex set of $V(M(H_n))$ as below.

$V_1 = \{e_1, e'_2, u_1, s_n\}$; $V_i = \{v_{i-1}, u_i, e_i, e'_{i+1} : 2 \leq i \leq n-1\} \cup \{s_{i-2} : 3 \leq i \leq n+1\}$; $V_n = \{v_{n-1}, s_{n-2}, e_n, e'_1\}$; $V_{n+1} = \{v, v_n, s_{n-1}, u_n\}$. Clearly $V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n, V_{n+1}$ are independent sets of $M(H_n)$. Also $|V_1| = |V_2| = |V_n| = |V_{n+1}| = 4$ and $|V_i| = 5$ ($3 \leq i \leq n-1$), it holds the inequality $\||V_i| - |V_j|\| \leq 1$ for every pair (i, j) . $\chi_{=}(M(H_n)) \leq n+1$. Since ve_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$) forms a clique of order $n+1$, $\chi(M(H_n)) \geq n+1$, $\chi_{=}(M(H_n)) \geq \chi(M(H_n)) \geq n+1$, $\chi_{=}(M(H_n)) \geq n+1$. Therefore $\chi_{=}(M(H_n)) = n + 1$. \square

Theorem 4.3 *If $n \geq 5$ the equitable chromatic number on total graph of Helm graph $T(H_n)$, $\chi_{=}(T(H_n)) = n + 1$.*

Proof Let $V(H_n) = \{v\} \cup \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\} \cup \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$ and $E(H_n) = \{e_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{e'_i : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\} \cup \{e'_n\} \cup \{s_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ where e_i is the edge vv_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$), e'_i is the edge $v_i v_{i+1}$ ($1 \leq i \leq n-1$), e'_n is the edge $v_n v_1$ and s_i is the edge $v_i u_i$ ($1 \leq i \leq n$). By the definition of total graph $V(T(H_n)) = V(H_n) \cup E(H_n) = \{v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{e_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{e'_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{s_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$.

Now, we partition the vertex set of $V(T(H_n))$ as below.

$V_1 = \{e_1, e'_2, u_3, v_n\}$; $V_2 = \{e_2, v_2, e'_3, s_n, u_4\}$; $V_i = \{e_i, v_{i-1}, e'_{i+1}, s_{i-2}, u_{i+2} : 3 \leq i \leq n-2\}$; $V_{n-1} = \{e_{n-1}, v_{n-2}, e'_n, s_{n-3}\}$; $V_n = \{e_n, v_{n-1}, e'_1, s_{n-2}\}$; $V_{n+1} = \{v, s_{n-1}, u_1, u_2\}$. Clearly $V_1, V_2, V_i, V_{n-1}, V_n, V_{n+1}$ ($3 \leq i \leq n-2$) are independent sets of $T(H_n)$. Also $|V_1| = |V_n| = |V_{n+1}| = 4$ and $|V_2| = |V_i| = 5$ ($3 \leq i \leq n-2$), it holds the inequality $\||V_i| - |V_j|\| \leq 1$ for every pair (i, j) , $\chi_{=}(T(H_n)) \leq n + 1$. Since ve_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$) forms a clique of order $n + 1$, $\chi(T(H_n)) \geq n + 1$, $\chi_{=}(T(H_n)) \geq \chi(T(H_n)) \geq n + 1$, $\chi_{=}(T(H_n)) \geq n + 1$. Therefore $\chi_{=}(T(H_n)) = n + 1$.

§5. Equitable Coloring on Gear Graph, Line Graph, Middle Graph and Total Graph

Theorem 5.1 *If $n \geq 3$ the equitable chromatic number of gear graph G_n , $\chi_{=}(G_n) = 2$.*

Proof Let $V(G_n) = \{v\} \cup \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{2n}\}$ where v_i 's are the vertices of cycles taken in cyclic order and v is adjacent with v_{2i-1} ($1 \leq i \leq n$).

Now, we partition the vertex set of $V(G_n)$ as below.

$V_1 = \{v\} \cup \{v_{2i} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\}$; $V_2 = \{v_{2i-1} : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$. Clearly V_1, V_2 are independent sets of (G_n) . Also $|V_1| = n+1$ and $|V_2| = n$, it holds the inequality $||V_i| - |V_j|| \leq 1$ for every pair (i, j) . $\chi_=(G_n) \leq 2$. $\chi(G_n) \geq 2$, $\chi_=(G_n) \geq \chi(G_n) \geq 2$, $\chi_=(G_n) \geq 2$. Therefore $\chi_=(G_n) = 2$. \square

§6. Equitable Coloring on Line Graph, Middle Graph and Total Graph of Gear Graph

Theorem 6.1 *If $n \geq 3$ the equitable chromatic number on line graph of Gear graph $L(G_n)$, $\chi_=(L(G_n)) = n$.*

Proof Let $V(G_n) = \{v\} \cup \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{2n}\}$ and $E(G_n) = \{e_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{e'_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2n-1\} \cup \{e'_n\}$ where e_i is the edge vv_{2i-1} ($1 \leq i \leq n$), e'_i is the edge $v_i v_{i+1}$ ($1 \leq i \leq 2n-1$), and e'_n is the edge $v_{2n-1} v_1$. By the definition of line graph $V(L(G_n)) = E(G_n) = \{v\} \cup \{v_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2n\} \cup \{e_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{e'_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2n\}$.

Now, we partition the vertex set of $V(L(G_n))$ as below.

$V_1 = \{e_1, e'_2, e'_{2n-1}\}$; $V_i = \{e_i, e'_{2i}, e'_{2i-3} : 2 \leq i \leq n\}$. Clearly V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n are independent sets of $L(G_n)$. Also $|V_1| = |V_i| = 3$ ($2 \leq i \leq n$), it holds the inequality $||V_i| - |V_j|| \leq 1$ for every pair (i, j) . $\chi_=(L(G_n)) \leq n$. Since e_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$) forms a clique of order n , $\chi(L(G_n)) \geq n$, $\chi_=(L(G_n)) \geq \chi(L(G_n)) \geq n$, $\chi_=(L(G_n)) \geq n$. Therefore $\chi_=(L(G_n)) = n$. \square

Theorem 6.2 *If $n \geq 5$ the equitable chromatic number on middle graph of Gear graph $M(G_n)$, $\chi_=(M(G_n)) = n+1$.*

Proof Let $V(G_n) = \{v\} \cup \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{2n}\}$ and $E(G_n) = \{e_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{e'_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2n-1\} \cup \{e'_n\}$ where e_i is the edge vv_{2i-1} ($1 \leq i \leq n$), e'_i is the edge $v_i v_{i+1}$ ($1 \leq i \leq 2n-1$), and e'_n is the edge $v_{2n-1} v_1$. By the definition of middle graph $V(M(G_n)) = V(G_n) \cup E(G_n) = \{v\} \cup \{v_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2n\} \cup \{e_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{e'_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2n\}$.

Now, we partition the vertex set of $V(M(G_n))$ as below.

$V_1 = \{e_1, v_2, e'_{2n-4}, e'_{2n-1}\}$; $V_2 = \{e_2, v_1, v_4, e'_{2n-2}\}$; $V_3 = \{e_3, v_3, e'_1, v_6, e'_{2n}\}$; $V_i = \{e_i, e'_{2i-5}, v_{2i-3}, v_{2i} : 4 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{e'_{2i-8} : 5 \leq i \leq n\}$; $V_{n+1} = \{v, e'_{2n-6}, v_{2n-1}, e'_{2n-3}\}$. Clearly $V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n, V_{n+1}$ are independent sets of $M(G_n)$. Also $|V_1| = |V_2| = |V_{n+1}| = 4$ and $|V_i| = |V_3| = 5$ ($5 \leq i \leq n$), it holds the inequality $||V_i| - |V_j|| \leq 1$ for every pair (i, j) . $\chi_=(M(G_n)) \leq n+1$. Since ve_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$) forms a clique of order $n+1$, $\chi(M(G_n)) \geq n+1$, $\chi_=(M(G_n)) \geq \chi(M(G_n)) \geq n+1$, $\chi_=(M(G_n)) \geq n+1$. Therefore $\chi_=(M(G_n)) = n+1$. \square

Theorem 6.3 *If $n \geq 5$ the equitable chromatic number on total graph of Gear graph $T(G_n)$, $\chi_=(T(G_n)) = n+1$.*

Proof Let $V(G_n) = \{v\} \cup \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{2n}\}$ and $E(G_n) = \{e_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{e'_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2n-1\} \cup \{e'_n\}$ where e_i is the edge vv_{2i-1} ($1 \leq i \leq n$), e'_i is the edge $v_i v_{i+1}$ ($1 \leq i \leq 2n-1$),

and e'_{2n} is the edge $v_{2n-1}v_1$. By the definition of total graph $V(T(G_n)) = V(G_n) \cup E(G_n) = \{v\} \cup \{v_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2n\} \cup \{e_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{e'_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2n\}$.

Now, we partition the vertex set of $V(T(G_n))$ as below.

$V_1 = \{e_1, e'_2, v_4, v_{2n-1}\}$; $V_2 = \{e_2, v_1, e'_4, v_6\}$; $V_i = \{e_i, e'_{2i-5}, v_{2i-3}, e'_{2i}, v_{2i+2} : 3 \leq i \leq n-1\}$; $V_n = \{e_n, e'_{2n-5}, v_{2n-3}, e'_{2n}\}$; $V_{n+1} = \{v, v_2, e'_{2n-1}, e'_{2n-3}\}$.

Clearly $V_1, V_2, V_i, V_n, V_{n+1}$ ($3 \leq i \leq n-1$) are independent sets of $T(G_n)$. Also $|V_1| = |V_2| = |V_n| = |V_{n+1}| = 4$ and $|V_i| = 5$ ($3 \leq i \leq n-1$), it holds the inequality $||V_i| - |V_j|| \leq 1$ for every pair (i, j) , $\chi_=(T(G_n)) \leq n+1$. Since $v e_i$ ($1 \leq i \leq n$) forms a clique of order $n+1$, $\chi(T(G_n)) \geq n+1$, $\chi_=(T(G_n)) \geq \chi(T(G_n)) \geq n+1$, $\chi_=(T(G_n)) \geq n+1$. Therefore $\chi_=(T(G_n)) = n+1$. \square

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